

Converged 5G/6G access-metro network combining RoF and coherent PONs

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ABSTRACT

The deployment of 5G and the anticipated 6G technologies impose novel challenges to existing time division multiplexing-passive optical network (TDM-PON) access infrastructures, requiring stringent QoS. To address this, we propose a hybrid access-metro network with numerous high-density ultra-dense wavelength division multiplexing (udWDM) and radio over fiber (RoF) PONs. There, one type of PON is based on power splitters, using lightpaths with coherent transmissions; while another type, based on arrayed wavelengths gratings (AWGs), supports RoF. Both converge to a metro network through optical nodes. All remote radio heads (RRHs) at base stations connect to a centralized optical line terminal (C-OLT) at the central office (CO), managing a centralized/cloud radio access network (C-RAN). This integrated design provides reconfigurable capabilities, optimizes efficiency and minimizes latency for new wireless technologies.

Keywords: 5G/6G, udWDM-PON, coherent transceivers, RoF, x-haul, C-RAN.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the network evolution relies on emerging 5G/6G wireless technologies with seamless connectivity for everything from remote work to smart cities, offering faster speeds, lower latency, greater capacity and enhanced energy efficiency. In a centralized/cloud radio access network (C-RAN) with “x-haul” interfaces, the mobile front-haul (MFH) links the remote radio heads (RRHs) to the baseband units (BBUs) for data processing, while the mobile back-haul (MBH) joins the BBUs and the core network (Fig. 1, a), offering advantages through coordinated networking strategies. To enhance operational efficiency amidst growing complexity, open RAN (O-RAN) promotes interoperability, flexibility, and innovation by disaggregating hardware and software components [1], deploying virtualized network functions (VNFs) and software-defined networking (SDN) principles. These digital radio-over-fiber (D-RoF) interfaces are standardized with functional split options in O-RAN flexible architectures. On the other hand, analog radio-over-fiber (A-RoF), transporting physical layer radio frequency (RF) signals on the MFH, may provide more resourcefully low latency and spectral efficiency demands.

In this work we will consider both digital and analog interfaces as in [2], but now supported by passive optical networks (PONs), built with power splitters and arrayed waveguide gratings (AWGs), respectively. The digital PON will be based on coherent transceivers, profiting their excellent sensitivity and spectral efficiency by ultra-dense wavelength division multiplexing (udWDM), while the A-RoF will carry the analog wireless waveforms in native format at an intermediate frequency (IF) multiplexed in WDM. Both types of networks will be merged in a metro ring topology converging in an access-metro network where all RRHs will be jointly served by a centralized-optical line terminal (C-OLT) located at the central office (CO), which furnishes reconfigurable capabilities.

This article is organized in the following sections: section 2 introduces the C-RAN and O-RAN architectures with their functional split options, the digital and analog MFHs and the corresponding proposed access architectures; in section 3 the access-metro architecture is presented, the loss budget in the network is evaluated and the capacity and network bandwidths are estimated; finally, in section 4 the conclusions are discussed.

Figure 1. a) C/O-RAN for an access-metro MFH/MBH network. b) O-RAN functional split options.

2. OPEN RADIO NETWORK

2.1 Digital and analog mobile front-hauls

O-RAN is a model based on standardization and interoperability of RAN elements, including an interconnection standard and open source software. The MFH has up to 10 functional split options, where split option 8 is C-RAN; however, to relax the MFH bandwidth (BW) requirements and with latency limited to a sub-ms range, some functions, such as processing, are left to the RRH, but at expenses of some degree of centralization [1]. There are three logical entities: open central unit (O-CU), open distributed unit (O-DU) and open radio unit (O-RU). The O-CU executes near-real-time roles, while the O-DU manages the radio link control (RLC) and the medium access control (MAC) real-time functions (Fig. 1,a) [1]-[3]. The entities O-CU and O-DU are linked with F1 interface and form the BBU of the C-RAN and, finally, the O-RU at the RRH completes the rest of the physical layers; like coding, Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and RF modulation; which are implemented in a specialized hardware. This D-RoF MFH requires analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) and digital-to-analog converters (DACs) at the O-RU.

While C-RAN connects digitally BBU to RRH via the Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) based on TDM, O-RAN provides the option to interface O-DUs and O-RUs by the enhanced CPRI (eCPRI), transporting Ethernet (Eth) packets and splitting functions and, therefore, reducing dramatically the BW because part of the baseband processing is located at the O-RU, but increasing the O-RU cost [4]-[5], as shown in Fig. 1,b.

Contrarily, in A-RoF MFH a multi-carrier radio signal is transmitted on a RF carrier or on an Intermediate Frequency (IF), and DACs and ADCs are removed, reducing latency, costs and hardware, and, furthermore, the BW is reduced achieving high spectral efficiency because the occupied BW is the same as the original signal [2].

In both D-RoF and A-RoF MFHs, advanced functionalities, such as coordinated multipoint (CoMP) transmission and reception, massive multiple-input-multiple-output (MIMO), non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) and optical beamforming, can be implemented to enhance the performance of deprived users and cells.

2.2 Access architectures

The proposed D-RoF access network is based in udWDM-PON with coherent homodyne detection. The user's optical network unit (ONU), where the RRH is attached, employs two tunable lasers (TLs) based on DFB-lasers with limited thermal tunability, one as local oscillator in the receiver (Rx) and another TL as transmitter (Tx), with direct or external modulation and two wavelengths (λ s) or lightpaths. The optical line terminal (OLT) implements the same reciprocal design for each ONU, while the optical distribution network (ODN), built with power splitters, coexists with legacy systems (Fig. 3). The TLs have non-preselected λ s with statistical uniform distribution in the working band. DFB-lasers have typically a linear λ -variation with temperature of about 0.1 nm/°C between 14 to 55 °C, covering 4 nm and tuning up to 80 channels of 6.25 GHz BW by a thermo-electric cooler (TEC) or Peltier, within the C or L-bands [6]. This network has been evaluated for different band organizations and dynamic wavelength allocation, and specifically in an implementation for smart activation with paired-lasers for Rx/Tx with a fixed λ -difference of 50 GHz with a basic band of 400 GHz in up/down sub-bands of 50 GHz [7]. The BW of each user in the PON can be different depending on the Class of Service, adapted to the corresponding bit rate by using typical Eth bit rates, because it is a widespread technology and scales easily in switching and routing.

The A-RoF employs a laser diode (LD) with direct modulation as Tx and photodiode (PD) detection as Rx, with lower sensitivity than coherent transceivers; hence, the architecture is realized with AWGs providing low insertion loss (IL) and filtering the dedicated spectrum to each RRH (Fig. 2) [8]. The RF carrier is $f_{RF} = 26$ GHz in the 24.25-27.5 GHz mm-wave band (n258 EU band), and the modulation can be n-QAM or orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), with 0.5 GHz BW in time division duplex (TDD) and unique RF for downstream (DS) and upstream (US). Then, the AWG channel spacing is 50 GHz, with up to 90 ports in C or L-bands, but a maximum of 80 is used because of BW limitation of optical amplifiers (OAs). A key element is the optical subcarrier shifter (OSS), built with circulators and OAs, and including a Mach-Zehnder modulator biased at the Null Point (NP-MZM), for the simultaneous frequency shifting of the WDM DS from IF to the wireless band, so that at the RRH the received signal by the PD can be radiated to the antenna without any processing [9].

Figure 2. A-RoF access architecture based on AWGs and spectra before/after optical subcarrier shifter (OSS).

Since the photodetected signal at the RRH is the result of the beating of the two optically generated sidebands, the RF frequency is doubled. The PD sensitivity is greatly dependent on its BW, and then for the RF band (DS) we will consider -15 dBm, whereas for IF (US) we will set it at -20 dBm. The Tx power of the OLT LD (once modulated) is of 7 dBm for both DS/US, and the resulting maximum loss budget (LB) is 22 dB for DS and 27 dB for US. In DS the losses in splitter, AWG, circulator and NP are of 3.5, 7, 1 and 10 dB, respectively; with 10 km optical fiber (OF) of 0.25 dB/km and 14.5 dB OA gain, the resulting LB is of 21 dB. For US without OA nor NP-MZM, the LB obtained is of 25.5 dB, so the OA is not needed. In DS for only one RRH the output power of the OA is of 0 dBm, but for 80 active RRHs it reaches 19 dBm, which is lower than the saturation power of 22 dBm.

3. CONVERGED ACCESS-METRO NETWORK

3.1 Converged access-metro architecture

In the CO the DS/US signals from all RRHs are connected to a pool of BBUs by an electronic switch (ES), where the BBUs manage the RRHs and interconnect them with the core network. If the RRHs to be coordinated are connected to different BBUs, they interchange information via the X2 interface. Now, to go further converging both D-RoF and A-RoF technologies, we propose the CONverged FLeXible Optical access network for 6G mobile Connectivity (CONFLOC). There, all RRHs are attached optically to a C-OLT at the CO in an access-metro C/O-RAN, providing network operation, reconfigurable capabilities, improving efficiency and reducing latency.

The access networks from both RoF types are connected to a metro ring by optical nodes (ONs) (Fig. 3). The udWDM-PON can serve conventional users, which are attended in a local OLT (L-OLT), and D-RoF RRHs connected to the C-OLT via the metro ring. The L-OLT uses the C-band, while the RRHs operate in the L-band. An optical bandpass filter (OBF) selects bands for L-OLT and C-OLT services. The L-OLT can also be of EPON/GPON type and it can as well insert DS/US lightpaths in L-band to the ring if needed by an optical coupler (OC). If the udWDM-PON is devoted only to D-RoF, then the OBF and the OLT are not needed. The other A-RoF type is also connected to the metro ring by ONs and operates in the C-band; therefore, in the ring both D-RoF and A-RoF converge at the C-OLT at different L and C-bands respectively. The MFHs inserted into the metro ring reach an assigned BBU in the C-OLT by means of an ES, which interconnects them to the core network.

The ON in the ring is composed by an OC with a XX/YY coupling ratio (CR), and an optical switch (OS) to choose the ring direction, East (E) or West (W). In case of an open ring, we have a bus topology, but without resilience. The OS can be remotely driven with the light of the OF and then the ON in the ring can be passive [10].

The C-OLT is attached to the ring by a double splitter and its architecture is equal to the basic udWDM-PON D-RoF plus the A-RoF OLT part. There, an ES furnishes versatile any-to-any connections between RRHs and BBUs and the MBH communication between BBUs is realized by the X2 interface. Moreover, the BBUs are assigned dynamically and turned on/off depending on the traffic; therefore, allowing energy efficiency; besides, connecting coordinated RRHs within a single BBU reduces the MBH data exchange and decreases the latency [11]. Finally, the ES is connected to the core router by an internet router (IR), the C-OLT controls the wavelength assignments by MAC messages C-OLT-ONUs/RRHs and the whole orchestration can be operated by SDN.

Figure 3. D-RoF and A-RoF CONFLOC access-metro network architecture for reconfigurable C/O-RAN.

3.2 Loss budget, capacity and network bandwidths

In order to minimize the LB in the access-metro network, the XX/YY CR of the ONs is to be selected. The LB has been calculated for different number of ONs and N -split PON ratios of 16, 32 and 64. The total OAs gain is of 30 dB (15 dB at both L-OLT and C-OLT), the OBF has a loss of 1 dB, each 2-split has a total loss of 3.5 dB and the OF distance is of 10 km. The results arise a trade-off between the number of ONs and the CR of the OC: a CR of 10/90 is chosen because it minimizes the LB for a number of nodes (Q) of 8 and 10 (Fig. 4 for $N = 16$ and 32).

For D-RoF access, considering a receiver sensitivity of -42 dBm with coherent detection and a transmitter TL power of 3 dBm, the LB has to be less than 45 dB. With a CR of 10/90, the LB has been evaluated in the converged network for the worst case, crossing all nodes, as a function of distance for 16, 32 and 64 split ratios with a total OAs gain of 30 dB (Fig. 5). For 10 km OF, maximum distance to keep the total latency in the sub-ms range, the LB is achieved for up to 16 ONs (excluding C-OLT) for $N = 16$ and 32, and for 12 ONs for $N = 64$.

Regarding A-RoF access, the LB is evaluated for both DS and US, with a maximum LB of 22 and 27 dB, respectively. Now the achieved number of ONs for 10 km, with total OAs gain of 36 and 22 dB, for DS and US respectively, is only up to 8 (Fig. 6). A typical configuration can be 4 ONs with 16-split of D-RoF (64 RRHs) and 4 ONs with 20-port AWG of A-RoF (80 RRHs), giving a maximum of 144 RRHs served by the C-OLT.

The number of RRHs connected to the converged network, N_{RRH} , depends on the number of deployed PONs and ONs. If the udWDM-PON serves conventional users and RRHs with a percentage of RRHs in each PON, P_{RRH} , and Q_D D-RoF ONs in the ring; then, for $N = 64$, a percentage of 12.5% and 8 ONs, $N_{RRH} = N \times P_{RRH} \times Q_D = 64 \times 0.125 \times 8 = 64$ RRHs of D-RoF type and the C-OLT will require $S = 64$ coherent transceivers. This is equivalent to PONs serving only RRHs with 4 ONs of 16-split or 2 ONs of 32-split PONs. If more RRHs are introduced in the PONs, a higher split degree in the C-OLT is required. Concerning the A-RoF access, a maximum of 80 RRHs is available, which can be distributed in 1, 2 or 4 ONs with AWGs of 80, 40 or 20 ports each, respectively.

Figure 4. Loss budget (LB) versus the coupling ratio XX/YY of the optical coupler and the number of nodes (Q).

Figure 5. Loss budget (LB) for D-RoF as a function of the distance and the number of nodes (Q).

Figure 6. Loss budget (LB) for A-RoF as a function of the distance and the number of nodes (Q).

To calculate the number of needed BBUs, N_B , first we evaluate the number of ports of the BBU, N_U , which depend on the BBU processing capacity, C_{BBU} , and on the bit rate of the physical layer split interface, B_{PLS} : $N_U = C_{BBU} / B_{PLS}$ [11]. With e.g. $C_{BBU} = 40$ Gb/s and $B_{PLS} = 5$ Gb/s, $N_U = 8$ ports/BBU. Then, for 64 D-RoF RRHs $N_{BD} = 64/8 = 8$ BBUs. Similarly, for 80 A-RoF RRHs and same bit rate, $N_{BA} = 80/8 = 10$ BBUs, giving a total of $N_B = N_{BD} + N_{BA} = 18$ BBUs. The BBUs are assigned dynamically depending on the traffic of the network, and if the RRHs are turned off because of inactivity period, the corresponding BBUs are also disabled and the remaining operating RRHs are reassigned to active BBUs to keep the working BBUs as few as possible for energy efficiency.

Regarding the required BWs, for the local udWDM-PON with coherent transceivers, the needed BW is of 400 GHz or 800 GHz for 32 or 64 users of 6.25 GHz, organized in 8 or 16 DS/US 50 GHz channel sub-bands for paired Rx/Tx TLs, respectively [7]. This BW can be extended to up to 950 GHz with TLs with limited tunability or with users of 12.5 GHz. Hence, the C-band (1530-1562 nm) with up to 80 channels of 50 GHz may be employed.

Concerning D-RoF access, the RRHs in the udWDM-PON will use the L-band: with 12.5 and 25 GHz channel BWs, B_{PLS} of up to 10 and 20 Gb/s, respectively, may be transported; taking 64 RRHs with 25 GHz BW, the required total BW is $2 \times 25 \times 64 = 3200$ GHz (64 channels of 50 GHz). Considering a total spectrum of 80 channels of 50 GHz BW in L-band (1575-1607 nm), still some BW is left for some RRHs using an extended 50 GHz channel BW. Regarding A-RoF, the C-band is planned for the converged network: with 80 channels of 50 GHz, the BW is of 32 nm (1530-1562 nm) in C-band. Both planned BWs in C and L-bands fit the typical gain BW of OAs.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A converged access-metro for 5G/6G combining digital radio-over-fiber (D-RoF) and analog radio-over-fiber (A-RoF) has been presented. In access the D-RoF uses coherent transceivers with high sensitivity in an udWDM-PON based on power splitters, while the A-RoF employs AWGs, profiting their filtering property and their low insertion loss. The RRHs use the eCPRI with functional split MFH interface in the D-RoF, and a multicarrier signal on a RF carrier in the A-RoF keeping the same BW as original signal, thus avoiding ADCs and furnishing low latency. Both D-RoF and A-RoF converge in a metro ring, reaching a centralized OLT (C-OLT) with resiliency. The BBUs are attached to the ring at the C-OLT in a C/O-RAN that provides CoMP functionalities.

The RRHs are connected to the BBUs by an ES and they are assigned dynamically depending on the traffic, thus providing energy/processing efficiency; besides, all network operations can be orchestrated by SDN. Finally, the loss budget, the capacity and the bandwidth have been evaluated demonstrating the feasibility of the network.

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